

ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF INSURANCE MARKET DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN ON MACROECONOMIC STABILITY

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes the development of the insurance market in Uzbekistan and its impact on macroeconomic stability. The study highlights the role of the insurance system in risk management, its importance in supporting investment processes, and its role in ensuring the stability of the financial system. It also examines the current state of the insurance market, development trends, and existing problems, and proposes ways to address them. The results of the study show that further development of the insurance market can strengthen the stability of the national economy.

Keywords: Insurance market, macroeconomic stability, risk management, insurance premiums, financial stability, investment activity, compulsory insurance, voluntary insurance, capitalization, insurance company, insurance supervision, regulatory framework, insurance services, economic security, market competition.

To date, the insurance sector has become one of the priority areas in the development of the country's financial sector. Taking into account the incomparable role of insurance in economic stability and social protection of the population in a market economy, in order to further develop the insurance market, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted Resolution No. 618 dated April 10, 2007 "On measures for further reform and development of the insurance market". This resolution gave a great impetus to the development of the insurance sector in the country and set out the directions for the development of the insurance market and legislation on insurance activities. It can be said that the adoption of this resolution marked the beginning of a new stage in the development and improvement of the insurance market.

In accordance with the Program for Reforming and Developing the Insurance Market in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2007–2010, the Presidential Decree provides for the implementation of a number of measures in the following areas:

further improve the legislative and regulatory framework for insurance, insurance activities and insurance supervision; expand the volume, types and quality of insurance services; ensure the transparency and reliability of the domestic insurance market, increase the level of capitalization of insurance companies, strengthen their financial stability and solvency; improve the system of training, retraining and advanced training of industry personnel.

In order to unconditionally implement the tasks set out in this Presidential Decree, extensive work is being carried out to improve modern types of insurance services, increase the quality of insurance activities, gradually strengthen the level of capitalization and financial stability of insurance companies, as well as introduce international standards into the process of regulating and controlling insurance activities. A study of the insurance market in Uzbekistan showed that the insurance sector in the country is developing quite rapidly. All key indicators of insurance companies are growing: the volume of collected insurance premiums, payments made, and insurance obligations are increasing. At the same time, the number of professional

participants in the insurance market is also increasing: insurance companies, insurance brokers, assistance companies.

The low demand for insurance services is not due to the lack of population and business entities, but to other factors. Currently, one of the main trends in the insurance market is the expansion of mandatory insurance types. However, there are two main risks associated with this trend. The first is an increase in transaction costs for businesses, which contradicts the government's policy of improving the business environment and reducing the tax burden. The second is the crowding out of voluntary insurance by mandatory insurance, which can have long-term negative consequences for the insurance market and the economy as a whole. Therefore, in developed countries, mandatory insurance types are introduced cautiously and gradually.

In theory and practice, such rules have been developed that compulsory insurance is usually introduced when damage is caused not only to the insured, but also to third parties as a result of an insured event. This applies, first of all, to civil liability insurance and fire insurance of buildings. In cases where the risk belongs only to the insured himself, compulsory insurance is usually not applied. It is not advisable to introduce new types of compulsory insurance when the Law “On Compulsory Insurance of Civil Liability of Vehicle Owners” has been in force for at least five years. It is necessary to thoroughly study the positive and negative effects of this law on insurers and insureds and develop a national model of compulsory insurance on this basis.

The existing “conditional” insurance system in Uzbekistan (compulsory insurance based on a contract) negatively affects competition in the insurance market and limits the ability of policyholders to freely choose an insurance company. This is especially evident when entrepreneurs receive loans. In order to reduce the negative impact of the “linkage” between banks and insurance companies, it is necessary to introduce a system of accreditation of insurance companies by banks. The terms of such accreditation should be clear and transparent, and the list of accredited insurance companies should be publicly announced. In order to ensure stronger competition between insurance companies, it would also be useful to allow commercial banks to sell products of any insurance company through their retail branches. In “conditional” insurance, the insured and the beneficiary are often different persons. In some cases, when an insurance contract is concluded to obtain a license for a certain activity or to register an export contract, the insurance interests of state bodies become unclear. It is necessary to restrict the mandatory conclusion of insurance contracts for state services through regulatory documents.

The low demand for insurance is also due to the lack of awareness among the population and business entities about the need to protect themselves from risks, the low willingness to allocate the necessary funds, and the low competitiveness of insurance products compared to other savings methods. Such alternative methods include investing in real estate, purchasing foreign currency, bank deposits, or simple savings.

The low competitiveness of insurance products is explained in some cases by the inability of insurance compensation to fully cover the costs incurred as a result of an insured event, as well as by the lack of confidence of insurers in the payment of compensation within the time limit and in the amount specified in the contract. In some cases, standardization of insurance activities may be more effective than the development of mandatory legal norms. Therefore, it is necessary to develop unified standards for vehicle insurance, cargo insurance and

agricultural risks, and subsequently apply them to other types of mass insurance. The introduction of standards does not reduce the importance of methodological guidelines and model rules developed by the Insurance Supervision Authority under the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan, but rather complements them as a means of guiding insurance activities.

In conclusion, the development of the insurance market in Uzbekistan is of great importance in ensuring macroeconomic stability. The distribution of risks through the insurance system protects economic entities from various financial losses and strengthens economic stability. At the same time, the investment activities of insurance companies serve as an important source of financing for the real sector of the economy.

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